

Ongoing R&D Projects in Uljanik

Aktivni istraživački i razvojni projekti u Uljaniku

Dani Dundara^a, Obrad Kuzmanović^a, Vito Radolović^a, Josip Andrišić^{a,*}, Igor Lalović^{a,*}, Matthias Krause^b, Grit Ladage^b

^a Uljanik brodogradilište d.d., Flaciusova 1, Pula

^b Center of Maritime Technologies e. V. (CMT), Bramfelder Straße 164, 22305 Hamburg, Germany

* Josip Andrišić, josip.andrisic@uljanik.hr, +385 52 374 761

Abstract

This paper is a report of most important ongoing R&D projects and a preview of expected gains. The focus will be on two EU funded projects: HOLISHIP and RAMSSES.

HOLISHIP (HOListic optimisation of SHIP design and operation for life cycle) project aims at developing the next generation of flexible systems for the design and performance assessment of ships. It addresses the growing aspiration of the European maritime industry to take a holistic approach to design and operation of maritime assets. The project is organised in three clusters: Cluster 1 comprises work packages for improving methods and tools needed at all stages of design and operation, ranging from market analysis and system architecture via hydrodynamics and structures to machinery and Life-Cycle Cost assessment. Cluster 2 is devoted to integration platforms for Computer Aided Engineering, including optimisation, and virtual demonstration of vessel performance. Finally, cluster 3 brings together application cases that will utilise results from clusters 1 and 2, covering for instance RoPax (ULJANIK) and double-ended ferries, cruise ships, OSVs and research vessels.

RAMSSES (Realisation and Demonstration of Advanced Material Solutions for Sustainable and Efficient Ships) aims to foster the application of new materials in maritime and inland waterway applications by developing, demonstrating and validating 13 specific maritime products to prepare for commercial market uptake immediately after the project. An important aspect of the work of RAMSSES will be to develop a "fast track to approval" for the application of new materials in the maritime sector. ULJANIK team leads the demonstration case in RAMSSES that is addressed to the innovative components and modular lightweight systems for RO-RO vessels introducing FRP (Fibre reinforced plastic) pultruded profiles and FRP sandwich technology

Keywords: HOLISHIP, RAMSSES, holistic approach, new lightweight materials, EU projects

Sažetak

Članak je svojstveno izvješće najvažnijih aktivnih istraživačkih i razvojnih projekata sa pregledom očekivanih rezultata. Naglasak je na dva projekta financiranih od strane EU: HOLISHIP i RAMSSES.

HOLISHIP (HOListic optimisation of SHIP design and operation for life cycle) projekt nastoji razvijati fleksibilne sustave za projektiranje nove generacije i procjenu učinkovitosti tako razvijenih brodova. Odnosi se na rastuću želju europske pomorske industrije ka holističkom pristupu projektiranju i upravljanju pomorskom imovinom. Projekt je organiziran u tri klastera: Klaster 1 obuhvaća radne cjeline za poboljšanje metoda i alata potrebnih u svim fazama projektiranja i eksploatacije, u rasponu od analize tržišta do arhitekture sistema preko hidrodinamike i strukture trupa do strojeva i ocijene cijeloživotnih troškova. Klaster 2 je posvećen integracijskim platformama za računalno potpomognuto inženjerstvo, uključujući optimizaciju i virtualnu prezentaciju svojstava broda. Na kraju, klaster 3 povezuje slučajeve primjene koji će koristiti rezultate klastera 1 i 2, a koji se baziraju na npr. RoPax brodu (ULJANIK), trajektima sa dvostrukim krajem, putničkim brodovima, OSV-ima i istraživačkim brodovima.

RAMSSES (Realisation and Demonstration of Advanced Material Solutions for Sustainable and Efficient Ships) nastoji poticati primjenu novih materijala na brodovima za pomorsku plovību i plovību unutarnjim vodama razvojem, demonstriranjem i ocjenjivanjem 13 specifičnih proizvoda koji će se pripremiti za postavljanje na tržište odmah po završetku projekta. Važan aspekt RAMSSES-a je razvoj 'brzog pristupa odobrenju' za primjenu novih materijala u pomorskom sektoru. ULJANIK-ov tim vodi demonstracijski slučaj u sklopu RAMSSES-a koji se odnosi na inovativne komponente i lagane modularne sustave za RO-RO brodove uvodeći FRP (vlaknima ojačana plastika) pultrudirane profile i FRP sendvič tehnologiju.

Ključne riječi: HOLISHIP, RAMSSES, holistički pristup, novi lagani materijali, EU projekti

1. Introduction –HOLISHIP idea

Maritime assets such as ships and offshore platforms are typically associated with large investments and are not often built in large series. Where air, rail and road transport benefit from the scale effects of series production and considerable lead time of product development, this is mostly not the case for maritime products. Advanced product design needs to reflect constantly extended requirements and assure a flexible use and optimized performance over the entire life-cycle for varying operational conditions. This calls for largely improved design tools including multi-objective and multi-disciplinary optimization and, finally, virtual testing of the overall design and its components.

Today's need for one-of-a-kind designs often results in an insufficient knowledgebase, inadequate lead time for complete optimization cycles and an incomplete interplay between different design disciplines. Furthermore, there are uncertainties and changes in future operational requirements over an asset's life-time which needs to be taken up in a holistic life-cycle optimization. HOLISHIP addresses these shortcomings of present design processes (for maritime products) with a systems based approach.

The early design stage of any maritime product offers the widest range of solutions to be explored. It is at this design stage that the multi-disciplinary design approach has the highest flexibility and impact. 'Higher design freedom' and life cycle cost control at this preliminary design step allow optimizing product design, taking into account all requirements. Being faced with the need to reduce operational costs and environmental impact while at the same time increasing safety, the maritime industry urgently needs to take up new life-cycle based design concepts including means for virtual testing of products. It adds to the complexity of the problem that ship design is typically shared between design offices and yards in close cooperation with system / equipment suppliers, all requested to work on a design for optimal operational performance which increasingly becomes a prime selling point for a vessel.

HOLISHIP addresses these urgent industry needs by the development of innovative design methodologies, integrating design requirements (technical constraints, performance indicators, life-cycle cost, environmental impact) at an early design stage and for the entire life-cycle in an integrated design environment. Design integration will be implemented in practice by the development of integrated design s/w platforms and demonstrated by digital mock-ups and industry led application studies on the design and performance of ships, marine equipment and maritime assets in general. For achieving its goals, HOLISHIP formed a team of complementary partners contributing "cutting edge" expertise in all relevant areas affecting the design and particularly life-cycle aspects of maritime products.

2. HOLISHIP project general information

2.1. PROJECT CONSORTIUM

HOLISHIP project, full name ‘HOListic optimization of SHIP design and operation for life-cycle’, is funded under the Horizon 2020 Framework program.

The HOLISHIP Consortium is consisted of 40 partners gathering a significant number of EU research institutions, Classifications societies, Universities, yards, equipment manufacturers, software developers and ship operators:

Fig. 1 HOLISHIP project partners

2.2. PROJECT OBJECTIVES AND TARGETED RESULTS

The main HOLISHIP objective is to develop a design software platform, integrating specialized software packages through an integration platform. Software dealing with stability, hydrodynamics, structural analysis, building, operational and transport cost, life cycle cost will be interconnected through this platform which will perform design optimization at early design stage, taking into account all main technical and regulatory constraints.

In order to achieve such a complex task HOLISHIP will specifically address the following main objectives:

1. Develop Software (s/w) tools for multi-objective and multi-disciplinary holistic system optimization and integration to design ships and offshore structures for life-cycle operation.

2. Develop and test a Virtual Vessel Framework (VVF) to be used in the optimization of ship operation and concept validation studies resulting in more efficient and safe ships.
3. Improve ship design through improved operational feedback from complex ship systems into the design loop.
4. Achieve measureable life-cycle cost reductions through innovative holistic ship design and demonstrate this for typical European maritime industry applications.
5. Reduce ship development time and costs through innovative design optimization and integration of software procedures.
6. Demonstrate methods to find optimal and innovative ship configurations according to measurable technical performances and ship's operational performance indicators.
7. Proceed to the full exploitation of the Virtual Vessel Framework (VVF) after completion of the project to ensure continued use by the European maritime industry and improvements of the VVF.
8. Disseminate and exploit the results gained from the project for the benefit of the European maritime industry, the university education and training of young and other professionals.

Achieving these objectives, the following project results will become available:

9. Framework of methods and an integrated software platform for the multi-objective, multi-disciplinary and multi-fidelity optimization of ship design and ship operation, coupling existing and novel design software tools to improve ship design and operation while reducing the design and development time.
10. Library of multi-fidelity models and software tools for application in design optimization or in simulated virtual vessel operation.
11. Virtual Vessel Framework for embedded ship simulation.
12. A series of eight (8) Application Cases with associated Digital Mock-Ups (DMU), demonstrating the HOLISHIP design approach and for exploitation by the HOLISHIP industrial end users.

2.3. *PROJECT CLUSTERS*

The HOLISHIP approach brings together all relevant main disciplines of maritime product design under the umbrella of advanced parametric modeling tools and integrated software platforms enabling the parametric, multi-objective and multi-disciplinary optimization of maritime products. The approach includes: market analysis and demand, economic and efficiency considerations, hull form design, structural design, selection of prime movers and outfitting. It considers all fundamental steps of the traditional "ship – design spiral", which, however, are better illustrated today by a systemic approach, which is in the HOLISHIP PROJECT implemented in practice by a "synthesis of integrated design tools", as shown in figure 2.

Fig. 2 HOLISHIP design platform structure

The proposed HOLISHIP synthesis model follows modern Computer Aided Engineering (CAE) procedures and integrates techno-economic databases, calculation and optimization modules and s/w tools along with a complete virtual model which will allow the virtual testing before the building phase of a new vessel. Modern GUI and information exchange systems will allow the exploration of the huge design space to a much larger extent than today and will lead to new insights and promising new design alternatives. The coverage of the ship systems will not be limited to conceptual design, but extend also to relevant major onboard systems / components. Their assessment in terms of life-cycle performance is expected to build up further knowledge of suitable outfitting details, this being a highly relevant aspect especially for the outfitting-intensive products of European Shipyards.

Consequently, the project is structured into three main work clusters:

1. **Tool development:** methods and s/w tools for the individual design aspects will be developed and adapted to the intended automated use in the HOLISHIP integrated design platforms.
2. **Software Integration:** of s/w tools developed in Cluster 1 to be integrated into HOLISHIP design platforms and the Virtual Vessel Framework.
3. **Application Cases/Demonstrators:** in which the integrated s/w platforms will be applied to the design and operation of ship and other maritime assets and the use and benefit of the developed frameworks will be demonstrated.

This overall project structure is sketched in figure 3.

Fig. 3 HOLISHIP project structure

3. Uljanik in the HOLISHIP project

Uljanik started slowly shifting the production portfolio in 2008 from less sophisticated (chemical tankers, SUL bulk carriers, asphalt carriers, PCTC, RO-RO ships) to more complex and highly sophisticated vessels (dredgers, cable laying vessels, large jack – up platforms, Ro-PAXEs, cruising vessels) due to increasing competition in the Far East.

Consequences of that business decision are increased pressure on Basic Design Department (10 people) due to wide portfolio of products (60-70 designs per year of various ship types), increased pressure on Detail Design Department and Production Department due to small series production or even unique.

The decrease in production series leads to increased need for new tools, skills and know-how. Design timeframe is much shorter now, making the outsourcing of certain knowledge impossible (CFD, FEM). Optimizing process is also limited, partly with the timeframe and partly with the lack of optimization tools. Thus, strong need for improvement of the design process arose, bearing in mind that over 80% of building costs are determined in early phases of design.

Main objective for Uljanik shipyard is significant improvement of the design process (and consecutive production processes as well). This will be demonstrated on the RoPAX vessel design, in view of ever changing owner’s requirements, operational boundaries, new regulatory/safety issues and economic aspects (life cycle performance).

RoPAX vessels: very important products in the Uljanik shipyards portfolio and perfect ship type for design optimization tools demonstration.

Significant improvement of design process implies the ability to perform vessel design optimization within short period of time or, in other words, to increase the ability to investigate the higher number of design solutions within given timeframe.

According to experience in Uljanik shipyard there are few major types of design processes: ship owners acting as a customer, ship owners acting as a partner, building contract politically signed on basis of economic and trade cooperation between two countries or state owned shipping companies and development of typical product.

- Ship owner – customer: three separated design phases (preliminary, concept and contract phase), very limited timeframe for each phase, each phase is considered as a filter – high market pressure, no direct contact with the owner until the final phase, strict offer based on tender documentation – little freedom to the designer for optimization.

Usual timeframe for designs based on tender documentation:

- 5 days (or 1 week) for preliminary design phase – rough sketch of GA + really short TS explaining only basic systems + indication of price (possible range) – first filter
- 10 days (2 weeks) for concept design phase – GA + E.R. GA with as many details as possible + short TS with all systems included + price calculated according to budget price from suppliers and according to the structural and outfitting weight assessment – second filter
- one month for contract design phase (usually against 1 or 2 shipyards candidates left on the shortlist) – detailed GA + E.R. GA + detailed TS including details of all systems on board + detailed cost breakdown (for negotiations with the owner) – third and final filter
- Ship owner – partner: overlapping design phases with no strict boundaries between (especially when Letter of intent is signed in very early phase), timeframe for the design is much more relaxed, no market pressure, direct contact with the owner (much more involved in all design phases), the designer is given much more freedom for optimization. Examples from ULJ recent history: Jan de Nul group, Grimaldi group, Ray Car Carriers, Marflet etc.
- Uljanik intention: to improve ship owner – customer design process with concept and contract phase optimization, which is most common in last years and more demanding design process. The result of the HOLISHIP project must be in line with the Ship owner – customer design process, meaning that timeframes given for this type of design process must be achievable by the design process developed in HOLISHIP.

In order to achieve the above several sub-objectives must be accomplished:

- Set-up of owner's requirements, design objectives, assessment criteria, regulatory constraints and market conditions.
- Development of parametric models for ship design optimisation
- Implementation of design in optimisation software platforms
- Application studies for two RoPAX with alternative propulsion
- Review of results and development of demonstrators

At the moment Uljanik has finished the concept design phase for the Prototype ship which will serve as a basis for future HOLISHIP optimization process. Work done for concept design phase:

- list of Owner's requirements defined
- preliminary hull form 3D model for two alternatives, with and without twin skegs, for further hydrodynamic analysis
- both hull forms are imported and parametrized in optimization platform, ready for global (concept phase) and local modifications (contract phase), specifically bulb geometry and skeg inclination angle
- preliminary selection of objectives, constraints, free variables and range for global hull form optimization
- preliminary General Arrangement Plan for concept phase finished
- preliminary compartmentation and stability calculations (both intact and damage) created
- 2D structural model and main frame scantlings drawing finished, as the basis for structural weight assessment
- list of technological and production constraints finished which will be used for structural optimization
- detailed structural weight break-down for all major structural elements in cargo and passenger space, other spaces calculated with cubic number method, using in-house correction factor, derived from previous ships built in ULJANIK
- electric energy balance sheet done in order to design alternative propulsion and machinery concept

Main Particulars:

• L_{oa}	abt. 217 m
• L_{bp}	210.00 m
• B	32.20 m
• $D_{m.deck}$	9.65 m
• T_{design}	6.80 m
• $T_{scantling}$	7.00 m
• $DWT_{scantling}$	abt. 11000 t
• Lane meters	4600 m
• Passengers	1500
• Crew	70
• Main engines	4x10300 kW
• $Speed_{service}$	abt. 24.0 kn

Fig. 4 HOLISHIP RO-PAX prototype

3.2. Future activities

Next step in the project is setting up an optimization procedure with the optimization software taking the central role. This optimization is divided into two stages:

1. Concept design phase
2. Contract design phase

Concept design phase

The prototype hull geometry developed in the initial phase of the project is imported and parametrized in the optimization software. A set of design parameters is chosen for global hull form optimization for concept phase, such as main dimensions, longitudinal center of buoyancy ... The optimization software will produce a large amount of design variants and call specialized software packages which will perform their own calculations for each design variant (hydrodynamic, structural, building cost, seakeeping...). The result should be an optimal design from a holistic point of view, taking into account stability, hydrodynamics, structural analysis, building, operational, transport and life cycle cost. Single skeg and double skeg design variant will be optimized separately.

The work will be carried out in the Work Package 16 (WP16) and divided between 15 partners and led by Uljanik Shipyard. The list of partners with their respective contribution is shown in table below.

Table 1 WP 16 partners

Partner	Main contribution to WP16
HSVA	Hull hydrodynamic optimization, calm water hydrodynamic assessment
BUREAU VERITAS HYDROCEAN	Structural optimization, Rules based software, machinery energy efficiency analysis, power system simulations added resistance , S RTP
CMT	Building cost and producibility models, cluster III leader
CNR - INSEAN	Hydrodynamic loads assessment + Seakeeping analysis
ELOMATIC	Weight estimation
FRIENDSHIP SYSTEMS	HOLISHIP (CAESES) optimisation platform
HOCHSCHULE BREMEN	Customization of NAPA macros, design & optimization in concept design phase
NATIONAL TECHNICAL UNIVERSITY OF ATHENS	Customization of NAPA macros, design & optimization in contract design phase
TRITEC	Review of owner requirements, operational profile and optimisation objectives and review of optimisation results from ship owner point of view
ULJANIK	WP16 leader
UNIVERSITY OF LIEGE	Structural analysis model customization + structural weight

UNIVERSITY OF STRATHCLYDE	Weight estimation, manoeuvring
SINTEF	Operational profiling tool customization
CETENA	LCPA tool customization
ROLLS-ROYCE	Alternative propulsion system

Contract design phase

For the contract phase a similar approach as for the concept phase will be taken, but with more detailed refinements of the design. Detailed hull form optimization will be performed, focusing on stern and fore part optimization, as well as other appendages optimization. In this phase no changes of main dimensions should be made as this would change design and building costs significantly. Seakeeping analysis will be performed to include crew/passenger comfort indices

Hull structure will be further optimized, preferably with no frame/longitudinal spacing changes, as this would change bulkhead position affecting damage stability calculations, which is very sensible on this kind of ships. The focus will be on cargo space structure optimization (weight, painting area and producibility-wise).

At the end of the project a benchmark study will be performed, comparing the optimal design to the prototype.

4. Introduction – RAMSSES Idea

Innovative materials and their wider use are important to improve the life cycle performance of European built ships and maritime structures, to reduce their environmental footprint, to make the industry more competitive at a global scale and thus to create and maintain employment. Considerable progress in research and development as well as first commercial applications in recent years has been made. Good example are results from completed EU founded projects such as BONDSHIP, DE-LIGHT Transport, ThroughLife and ADAM4EVE. Uljanik implemented commercially results from the DE-LIGHT Transport project as modular composite Ro-Ro cargo decks on Pure Car Truck Carrier. Although the project was successfully completed, Uljanik experienced real life challenges to design and install advanced and lightweight materials in a vessel new building. Maritime sector, known as 'conservative', restrains the use of lightweight and other advanced materials, but the potential and benefits are driving the EU maritime industry, researchers and ship owners to take further steps.

This paper will try to present European Innovation Action RAMSSES and its endeavor to address the most relevant problems that hinder a broader and quicker technology uptake, thus to obtain recognition and an established role for advanced materials in the European maritime industry. The project comprises both practical measures that are dedicated to improving, assessing and showing the readiness of certain technologies, and strategic actions that aim at enhancing the innovation capability of the European maritime industry on the long run and in a sustainable manner. This paper discusses the particular problems that need to be tackled, and, in answer to those, the specific objectives RAMSSES has set itself. The industry driven demo cases pursued in the project are introduced, followed by a discussion of the expected impact. Furthermore, collaboration activities and opportunities are introduced.

5. RAMSSES challenges and objectives

RAMSSES gathers a wide consortium of EU partners with a common aim to provide answers to specific problems which everyone involved in material innovation and application is facing. For the three most relevant problems, specific project objectives have been defined. Each of the objectives corresponds with a set of activities which have been translated into layers of the ‘RAMSSES pyramid’ which represents the project structure, Fig. 5. The problems and objectives, as well as RAMSSES’s approach to respond is outlined in the sub sections below.

5.1. Foster the use of new materials in real applications with high market potential

Problem: When it comes to innovative material solutions, many ship operators, shipyards and suppliers are lacking confidence and awareness both of such designs’ long-term technical properties in maritime operation and economic benefits over the life cycle. There is no clear evidence that cost savings in ship operation can compensate potentially higher expenses for purchasing raw materials and applying more sophisticated life cycle processes. Consequently, industry uptake of new materials is lagging behind the potential.

RAMSSES’s answer: Market driven demonstrators. Shipbuilders and sub suppliers are leading 13 different demo cases, dedicated to show the variety of innovative materials, their suitability for maritime applications, and the related potential. To assess the particular solutions’ maturity but also to create confidence in advanced materials for maritime use in general, one physical demonstrator is built for each demo case, and tested on board or under realistic conditions. Demos in RAMSSES cover the entire maritime supply chain from component and equipment production through integration in complex products to repair. This is essential to optimize the entire process chain, to develop modular products, processes and procedures, and to reduce cost while maintaining high flexibility. These effects will be validated by an accompanying economic and environmental performance assessment.

Fig. 5 Layer structure within the RAMSSES project, and main objectives

5.2. Prove full technical and economic feasibility of the solutions using best practice, and consolidate knowledge

Problem: There is a lack of information and overview on available technical performance test data for innovative materials at lab scale and in realistic maritime environments. Consolidated and

harmonised design, testing, simulation and approval procedures are largely missing. The same applies for methods for life cycle performance assessment (LCPA – cost and environmental impact). Consequently, approval is carried out on a case-by-case basis, repeating risk assessment and testing, thus requiring extra time and cost.

RAMSSES's answer: Assessment teams take care of performing technical assessment, including destructive testing and on-board measurements, and LCPA in a harmonised way, using leading edge expertise and combining tests where appropriate. They take existing test results and experiences in maritime and other sectors into account and document the results of approval tests in a common data repository for future use in similar cases.

5.3. Support the maritime sector's innovation capabilities

Problem: Existing expert knowledge on innovative materials in the maritime field, as well as related test data etc. is widely distributed and difficult to access. Hence, a reduced awareness on 'what is possible' hinders commercial uptake of solutions by a wider community, and reduces economy of scale. The situation is caused by insufficient systematic knowledge exchange as well as trans- and intersectoral technology transfer. Current maritime rules and regulations do not consider the use of innovative materials appropriately; most applications require time consuming and costly case-by-case proof of equivalent safety versus conventional solutions.

RAMSSES's answer: In a knowledge and data repository, RAMSSES is collecting project results and information from external sources. In cooperation with existing initiatives, a Maritime Innovation Platform is being formed which helps to spread excellence to a wider community. Experience in practical applications, test data and a more efficient methodology to prove equivalent safety for new materials will feed into the rule making process and improve the expertise of the sector.

6. RAMSSES Innovative Solutions

Weather metallic, non-metallic or hybrid, new materials are finding their way to possible existing and new applications. Combining new materials and productions processes and possible applications on ship structures and outfitting gives a wide range of possibilities to improve existing solutions or to give completely new ones.

RAMSSES incorporates 13 specific demo cases with the goal to design and develop solutions for possible commercial applications. Each of the demo case development includes the elaboration of interfaces between novel and conventional structures, development and analyses of production and assembly concepts, definition of life cycle processes in maintenance, repair and end-of-life. Evidence of the solutions' feasibility, performance and readiness for approval will be given both by the production of physical demonstrators, and in the assessment of decisive technical properties, environmental impact and economic key figures. All physical demonstrators will undergo real-life tests which are undertaken either on board or in a close-to-reality environment.

Fig. 6 RAMSSES demo cases

Demo cases are divided in 3 clusters depending on different type of application:

- **Cluster 1 – Components and equipment:** Material and process innovation is focused primarily in the Component and Equipment demo cases. Fire retardant and bio-based materials are covered as well as innovative production techniques such as 3D printing, and upscaling of new construction principles like truss core panels. The solutions bear a high potential for SME suppliers.
- **Cluster 2 – Ship integration for non-metallic and multi-material structures:** The demo cases in this cluster are all facing the challenge to find solutions for integrating innovative materials into complex ship structures, and for integrating the required production and assembly processes into the manufacturing and supply chain.
- **Cluster 3 – Advanced steel structures and innovative repair methods:** Material innovation does not necessarily mean introduction of materials other than steel. The demo cases in this cluster are related to the application of innovative steel types, and repair methods for steel and others.

6.1. Modular Light System for Less Critical Internal Walls and Superstructure (Cluster 1, Component)

The conventional solution in this area foresees steel walls with external insulation to reach fire class A-0, coming with a mass about 50 kg/m² and cost up to 220 €/m², including insulation. Very rarely (primarily for non-SOLAS ships), FRP structures or foam-core panels are used which are produced and assembled mostly manually. Truss core panels and some connecting elements have been developed in previous projects at small scale, but no modular system for a wider range and industrialised production is available.

The demo case provides a modular standard system consisting of panels, connecting elements and outfitting elements (e.g. doors, windows, cables), produced in a highly automated winding process, allowing for easy assembly on-board, Fig. 7. Thanks to a high-performance carbon fibre truss structure, the solution comes with ultra-low mass ($\ll 10 \text{ kg/m}^2$), improved noise damping, and reduced raw material consumption (truss structure instead of low-density foam) at equivalent fire safety and equal cost to the conventional solution. There is a wide range of applications for the solution in various ships (PAX, ferries, deckhouses of cargo ships), offshore accommodation and in land based buildings. Further use of advanced truss-core structures in bridges and other applications is also possible.

6.2. *Lightweight Components for High Loads and Fire Class (Cluster 1, Component)*

The use of non-metallic lightweight structures for critical applications in SOLAS ships is very limited and not system based, even though their feasibility has been tested and pre-proven in previous projects. Projects in material sciences have demonstrated potentials of new raw materials (bio-based, fire retardant). However, the test results available are not sufficient for maritime approval. Production, assembly and outfitting processes are not developed to industry needs. Hence, steel structures are by far dominating.

Sustainable lightweight components largely using bio-based and other innovative raw materials are qualified for maritime use in this demo case. The system integrates advanced properties like reduced weight, fire safety equivalent to steel and improved thermal and acoustic insulation. The foreseen development comprises panels (FRP or foam filled sandwich), connecting and outfitting elements for critical applications, industrialised production and easy assembly. The target fire class is up to A-60 and B-30, with a thermal conductivity $< 0.4 \text{ W/mK}$, and a weighted sound reduction index $> 38 \text{ dB}$. The range of applications in ships and offshore includes decks, bulkheads, and walls. There is also a potential for use in rail vehicles and buildings, with a significant greening potential through bio-based and recyclable/reusable materials and components.

Fig. 7 truss core panels - (a) assembled structure; (b) winding process

6.3. *Propeller Blade made by Additive Manufacturing (Cluster 1, 3D-printing, Equipment)*

Large propellers are currently cast from metal, while smaller ones are occasionally made of composites. Additive Manufacturing (AM) technology is developed at lab scale and in industrial applications for highly complex and weight critical parts (e.g. in airplanes). AM of large parts (>1 m) with complex twisted skins and closed cavities is limited to several lab scale experiments. Fatigue properties and productivity do not meet maritime needs.

The demo case foresees development and proof of feasibility of a highly productive and reliable Wire Arc Additive Manufacturing (WAAM) process using different metal alloys, e.g. cupro-aluminium, martensitic or duplex steels. The process features a high deposit volume and a defect free and cost-efficient process. The demonstrator, coming with 1.5-2 m diameter and less weight through internal cavities, will be tested against fatigue and corrosion, while hydrodynamic properties are assessed by numerical simulation. The proof of functional and economic feasibility for maritime real-scale applications will catalyse the use of AM and the realisation of corresponding new design opportunities. The AM processes for large structures will be attractive for propellers and turbines in the maritime and energy sector, but also for offshore and general engineering.

6.4. *Lightweight Rudder Flap (Cluster 1, Equipment)*

Smaller rudders e.g. for leisure boats are occasionally made of FRP, while large rudders for container ships and tankers with a size of up to 100 m² are nowadays exclusively made of steel, resulting in heavy hinges, shafts and supports, and correspondingly high loads and energy demands. Increased freedom of design of a composite rudder flap can improve hydrodynamic performance, lifetime and reduce maintenance cost. High loads and a lack of experience in production processes currently inhibit the use of advanced materials.

The demonstrator in this case is a high performance, multi-material rudder with a lightweight flap, including its multi-material components, manufacturing, joints and joining technique. The solution provides improved hydrodynamic design up to potentially adaptive flap shapes at equal production and reduced maintenance cost. The demonstration campaign will comprise real-life operational validation on board and maintenance/repair tests. The solution is suitable for a wide variety of rudders, a considerable share of them produced in Europe, for different types of ships. Positive experiences will trigger applications of FRP e.g. for propulsion improvement devices and adaptive hull structures. Potential synergies to offshore, e.g. renewable energy devices are also expected.

6.5. *Internal Walls and Superstructure of Cruise Ships (Cluster 2, non-metallic)*

Steel and aluminium dominate current applications thanks to the vast related know-how, comprehensive existing approvals and established processes related to these materials, Fig. 6. Functional feasibility of non-metallic structures (mostly foam core sandwiches) was shown in R&D projects and limited industry applications. An industrialised process chain, including inspection and repair, is largely missing. External insulation and extensive approval requirements inhibit a wider, economically feasible application.

Using standardised elements (e.g. from corresponding RAMSSES component demo cases), this demo case focuses on the development of highly efficient processes for adaptation, assembly and outfitting of a modular system, and integrating this into the overall ship design and structures. Requirements for the envisaged applications comprise strength, fatigue, fire resistance, comfort, lightweight, optical appearance as well as easy, flexible and cost-efficient processes, allowing pre-outfitting and pre-fabrication of larger blocks. The application potential of lightweight modular walls and superstructure reaches several thousand m² in modern cruise ships. The system can also be adopted to ferries, yachts, offshore accommodation, and land-based buildings. Highly efficient

processes and pre-approval will pave way for the wider application of non-metallic and multi-material structures in other parts of the ship, including critical applications.

6.6. Modular Deck System for RoRo Vessels (Cluster 2, non-metallic)

Nowadays, steel and partly aluminium are the predominant solutions for RoRo decks. Innovative lightweight steel and steel-plywood decks are occasionally applied at small scale, primarily for liftable (intermediate) decks which do not contribute to global strength. Non-metallic composite sandwich deck panels in a steel frame structure are tested and shown in research, and few prototype applications at small scale exist. Assembly and outfitting processes are largely manual and not adapted to larger economy of scale.

The demo case solution is a system for cargo decks based on standard lightweight panels and metallic or pultruded (composite) beams, Fig. 9– including corresponding joints and outfitting elements (lashing devices, lifting elements etc.). Fabrication, assembly, outfitting and repair processes are developed. The target is to achieve an optimum between weight and payload, and production cost at reduced maintenance (corrosion). There are several thousand m² of cargo decks in typical RoRo ships, the mass of which can be further reduced. Using synergies and standardisation potential together with RAMSSES component demo cases, the application potential can be further increased.

Fig. 8 Extruded profiles production facilities

Fig. 9 FRP pultruded profiles geometry and arrangement – hypothetical solutions

6.7. Lightweight Walls for Work Boats (Cluster 2, multi-material – Aluminium/FRP)

Currently, a variety of steel or aluminium designs with external insulations is used for superstructures and deckhouses. Extruded aluminium pre-fabrications, often joined by friction stir welding, and composite walls, allow for modular pre-fabrication and assembly, including insulation, Fig. 10 (a). However, small shipyards often lack the required knowhow on optimal solutions, material processing and integration into their specific designs. The demo case envisages assessing, testing and integrating a variety of solutions using extruded aluminum and composite

panels for deckhouses and superstructures of small workboats under the specific conditions of a small shipyard. The aim is to use standardized modular lightweight systems. However, in comparison with the cruise and RoRo applications, solutions in small yards must work for single panels and provide high flexibility in design, robustness at low cost, considering limited skills and automation. There is a wide application potential especially for numerous small shipyards in Europe which produce a huge number of small vessels, often for local markets.

6.8. *Superstructure Module on a Steel Deck of Multi-Purpose Vessels (Cluster 2, multi-material – FRP/Steel)*

The demo case is dedicated to smaller, fast ships with highly specialized, high-value and sensitive outfitting, operating under extreme conditions ‘all year round at 24/7’ (e.g. offshore patrol, coast guard, or environmental surveillance vessels). For strength reasons, hulls of these ships as well as superstructures are usually made of steel or aluminium. Superstructures are basically exposed to extreme conditions, such as wash and green water, wind, vibration or temperatures. Composites would offer benefits such as lower weight, improved noise and vibration damping, or stealth effects. However, a lack of operational experience, condition monitoring and methods for a multi-criteria design optimization currently act as barriers to wider use.

The solution is a compact superstructure module consisting of FRP foam sandwich panels, with integrated joints to the metallic deck, outfitting elements and condition monitoring, including the necessary production, joining and repair techniques at competitive cost as well as an optimised design and approval approach for a variety of similar cases. Functional requirements include strength, fatigue, noise, vibrations, resistance to aging and survivability in case of fire. The demo case pushes the limits for current FRP applications across the sectors and enables wider applications in fast special ships for a variety of purposes, including in the offshore industry.

6.9. *Custom-Made Hull of an Offshore Vessel (Cluster 2, non-metallic)*

The demo case is a full-scale hull section for a large offshore vessel, operating under harsh environments under SOLAS conditions, including the internal elements, entirely from composite materials, replacing the current steel solution. ‘Ingredients’, such as materials, joints and joining techniques or solutions for equivalent fire safety are available from previous R&D and small-scale applications, but have never been tested, validated and approved in combination. Production processes for such large structures are still too expensive and partly not suitable for practical use under shipyard conditions.

A complete composite vessel is designed in line with SOLAS requirements and class rules. Production processes and quality assurance measures are developed, and a full-scale hull section (ca. 6m x 6m x 3m) is produced. To validate design parameters, a real-life destructive test will be performed on site under supervision of testing experts, class and flag states. Focus will be on integration of processes and components as well as on understanding and demonstrating real-life behavior. An additional effect is the decrease of current safety margins. Suitable test procedures, as well as structural health monitoring and calculation methods to gain approval, will be developed. The demo will result in the first approved FRP SOLAS ship. All in all, shipyards’, owners’, flag states’ and class societies’ trust in the feasibility of composite solutions for large commercial ships will increase dramatically; this particular demo case will also showcase a new approach to approval for future cases. Detailed knowledge on processes, design and testing is highly relevant for large load carrying composite structures in various applications, as well as in other sectors.

6.10. *Lightweight cabin area for Passenger Ships (Cluster 2, multi-material)*

Prefabricated modular cabins have largely replaced the ‘in-situ’ made cabins in cruise ships and ferries, Fig. 10 (b). Cabins usually come without a floor (which is still part of the steel structure),

making transport and installation difficult and restricting pre-outfitting. Piping and wiring is usually integrated in the steel structure, but not in the cabins. Windows and other sensitive elements can only be installed at a late stage, when the cabin is fully connected and integrated. Hence, there is still a margin for weight reduction and shipyard process improvement.

A fully integrated 'box-type' PAX cabin is developed, with extensive use of different lightweight materials, compact (space saving) design, and fully integrated outfitting and standard connectors to the global ship distribution system. The proof of full functional fitness comprises strength, noise and vibration, and fire, along with a new structural concept of the ship. Substantial mass savings (ca. 400 kg/cabin or 1.000 t/ship), cost savings (expected 5 M€ per ship) and flexibility in design (modular approach, cabins not integrated in the load bearing steel structure) are expected as well as reduced maintenance and refurbishment cost. The modular approach allows for combining standard elements to customer specific solutions. Prefabricated, self-sustainable cabins can be used for a variety of PAX ships, offshore accommodation, but also land-based buildings and ad-hoc (emergency) accommodation.

Fig. 10 (a) Extruded Aluminium profiles in a workboat, joined by friction stir welding; (b) Conventional passenger cabins without floor

6.11. *Highly Loaded Structural Details from High Tensile Low Alloy Steels for Cruise and Research Vessels (Cluster 3)*

Highly loaded parts in large ships (e.g. window corners in cruise ships, Fig. 11 (a) are currently strengthened with thick sections of conventional steel, or the design (e.g. radius of the notches) needs to be modified. High tensile steels (HTS) offer significant weight saving (5-20%, case-dependant), improved strength and more design freedom. While feasibility of HTS in shipbuilding has been shown in previous projects, joining processes and joint properties are currently weakening HTS structures and decreasing practical use.

Welding procedures, design variations and post-processing techniques (friction stir processing, over-lamination) are systematically investigated and tested to improve quality, fatigue life and corrosion behaviour of welds in design details of different HTS types, e.g. longitudinal bulkheads. Failure mechanisms and approval criteria are defined as well. Numerical simulation and statistical models will enhance process knowledge and help achieving optimised design and robust processes, thus to obtain pre-approval for similar applications. Smaller, real-scale specimens, sufficient to achieve fully valuable SN-curves, will be produced in realistic production environments. Methods and process knowledge developed in the demo are applicable for a wide variety of large structures in ships and offshore structures, including renewable energy devices. Further application is possible in land based steel structures, like bridges or buildings.

6.12. Lightweight Decks of High Tensile Steel in Cruise Ships (Cluster 3)

Weight saving through thinner structures or use of HTS is of increasing interest in modern cruise ships and feasible in principle. It is well known that production processes have significant impact on the quality of joints and structural distortions, which can decrease the structures' performance. While low heat input welding technology for conventional steel is in place, a lack of experience, quality assurance and confidence in the shipyard production processes does not allow for the extensive use of HTS in critical (load carrying) applications currently.

The demo case's mission is to show the feasibility of production of large steel sections using thin HTS material, Fig. 11 (b), ranging from butt and fillet welds in pre-manufacturing to assembly joints in confined spaces or overhead conditions within and outside covered facilities. Process parameters and QA procedures will be established under real-life conditions at real scale, providing the basis for approval and wider use of HTS thin sheet structures under full exploitation of their strength properties. Developing the required process skills and quality will provide competitive advantages, not only in terms of cost, but also in producing products with new design features and reliable quality. The use of HTS with yield strengths of up to 690 MPa is expected to allow weight savings of 20% and above at high cost efficiency, leading to reduced fuel consumption and increased payload. The processing of HTS in large structures under harsh environmental conditions is applicable not only to cruise ships, but also to highly loaded structures such as cranes, bridges and offshore renewable energy devices.

Fig. 11 (a) Curved cut-out to reduce notch effect; (b) steel deck structure; (c) composite patches being applied on welded steel specimens

6.13. Composite Overlay to repair and Improve Metallic and Non-Metallic Structures (Cluster 3)

In 30+ years of global operation under harsh environments, maritime products, especially tailor-made structures with decreased safety margins and new materials, need specific, easy to handle and low-cost repair technologies to be acceptable for owners and authorities. Composite patch overlamination was successfully tested in several projects, and has been applied e.g. for repair of aluminium aircraft structures as well as thick steel sections in offshore and pipelines, Fig. 11 (c). Composite patches work as crack arrestors for existing damages. Effects of composite overlamination to improve fatigue life of welded joints have been studied sporadically. No systematic design and processing guidelines is available.

For wider maritime applications, both for repair and joint fatigue improvement dimensioning, design, material selection and processing procedures are established on a systematic basis, and

verified by tests and parameter studies (statistical models) on fatigue, aging and corrosion, first at lab scale. This will serve as a basis for QA guidelines and approval by class societies. Tests will allow for directly comparing the effect of over-laminated specimens against untreated ones, as well as with the composite demos. Finally, real-life application tests and long-term monitoring of the effects will be carried out at a shipyard as well as on board a real ship. The solution will provide a comparatively easy-to-apply, robust and cheap method to extend the lifetime of many applications, within the maritime sector with its extreme environmental conditions, and beyond.

7. Conclusion

Involvement in R&D projects gives two main benefits to a company like Uljanik. **First** is gaining connections with various industry partners, universities, research institutes. **Second and most important is** gaining access to free knowledge giving the company an advantage against the competition. This is getting more important, as competition from the Far East is taking a greater share in building more complex ships and demand for newbuilding's is greatly diminished in the last few years.

Significant results were already achieved **by being involved** in R&D projects. The results of some of the projects were already implemented in built ships, proving the benefits gained from participating in such projects.

Uljanik is aiming to get an additional edge against the competition by implementing products developed in the RAMSSES project in future designs and by improving design procedures that will be developed in the HOLISHIP project.

Acknowledgements

The project HOLISHIP has received funding under the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the grant agreement No 689074.

The project RAMSSES has received funding under the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the grant agreement No 723246.

References

n/a